

**Memory, Melancholy, and Modernity: The Familial Fractures in Desai's
*Clear Light of Day***

A THESIS

**Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
BACHELOR OF ARTS IN ENGLISH**

VARENDRA UNIVERSITY

**বরেন্দ্র
বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়**

**Department of English
Faculty of Arts and Social Science**

Submitted by

Md. Mizanur Rahman

ID No: 221011053

Batch: 29th

Supervised by

Nayeem Al-Hasib

Assistant Professor

Department of English

Varendra University

December 2025

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Summer 2025

Supervised By:
Nayeem Al-Hasib
Assistant Professor
Department of English
Varendra University

Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to my parents, who always believed in me and kept my spirits high.

Declaration

I hereby declare that the thesis titled “Memory, Melancholy, and Modernity: The Familial Fractures in Desai’s *Clear Light of Day*,” submitted for the degree of BA Honors in English to the Department of English, Varendra University, is an original and independent research work. This thesis, in its entirety, has not been submitted for any other degree or certificate.

Md. Mizanur Rahman

ID: 221011053, 29th Batch

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BA in English

Department of English

Varendra University

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Abstract

This thesis offers a critical analysis of Anita Desai's *Clear Light of Day*, focusing on how memory, historical trauma, gendered silence, and the tension between tradition and modernity shape subjectivity and familial relationships within the Das family. Desai's non-linear narrative structure foregrounds the fluidity of time, allowing memory to function as a psychological and ethical force that constructs identity, governs emotional responses, and enables reconciliation. Also examines the indirect yet significant impact of the 1947 Partition, revealing how historical trauma infiltrates private life and fractures interpersonal bonds without occupying the narrative foreground. Another central thematic concern, Gendered silence emerges as both a mechanism of patriarchal repression and as a mode of endurance and moral resilience. Female characters, particularly Bim, sustain familial continuity through silence, sacrifice, and ethical steadfastness. Finally, the thesis explores the conflict between tradition and modernity through the symbolic space of the family home, which embodies continuity, memory, and emotional rootedness, while modern aspiration promises freedom but results in detachment. This research also aims to prove Desai's ultimate goal that reconciliation (personal and national) lies in acknowledging emotional responsibility, embracing memory, and negotiating the costs and values of both tradition and modernity.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Anita Mazumder Desai is an Indian novelist and a Professor of Humanities at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Her birth year is 24 June 1937, and the place is Mussoorie, India. Her mother was a German, and her father was a Bengali Indian. She grew up in Delhi within a multicultural environment, as her parents were from different cultural backgrounds. She portrays these multicultural aspects in many of her writings. *Cry The Peacock*, the first novel of Desai, was published in 1963. *Clear Light of Day*, published in 1980, and she considers this novel as her autobiographical work (Bim may represent the author herself), taking place in the same area where she grew up. Some of her works, including *Clear Light of Day (1980)*, *In Custody (1984)*, and *Fasting Fasting (1999)*, were all shortlisted for the Booker Prize. She won the British Guardian Prize for *The Village by the Sea*, and also received a Sahitya Academy Award in 1978 for her novel *Fire on the Mountain*.

Particularly, the novel *Clear Light of Day* is divided into four parts and represents different timelines, from the past to the present. The first part of the novel started in the 1980s (Distance), the second part started in the 1930s (Seeds of Conflict), the third part started in the 1940s (Idealised Memories & Innocence), and the final part came back to the 1980s (Reconciliation and Understanding) again. Desai uses various timelines to explore how memory can change over time and form identity through recollection.

Clear Light of Day is frequently explored family dynamics set against the backdrop of Old Delhi in the late 1960s and early 1970s. The story delves into the themes of family, memory, guilt, and self-discovery as the characters navigate the complexities of their relationships, particularly with their estranged brother Raja, who has pursued a different life.

Desai explores the partition of India and Pakistan in 1947 in the novel. This partition led to a broken condition in India, around 300,000 Muslim migrants left Delhi, and 500,000 non-Muslim came from Pakistan. This situation creates several social issues, such as identity crisis, cultural clash, family fragmentation, emotional distance, Hindu and Muslim conflict, growing refugee in all over the country, etc. This animosity among different caste and religious groups was exacerbated by the British policy of “divide and rule” (Gairola, 2017, p. 124). Desai portrays the Das Family’s conflicts as a metaphor for the separation of Hindus and Muslims as Tara and Raja move away permanently just after the partition. As it has been noted, “*Clear Light of Day* gives its audience a localized view of history in the sense that it illustrates the profound consequences of the Partition on the members of the Das family” (Osman, 2015, p.15). Not only that, Hyder Ali Sahib, the Das family’s Muslim landlord, leaves Delhi with his family for Hyderabad, which also implies the effects of partition and family fragmentation.

Thus, the central concern of this research is to explore the fluidity of time and memory, personal trauma, and the historical context of the novel in shaping family dynamics, the emotional distance (fragile emotional bonds), and the tension between tradition and modernity (Old Delhi’s decaying traditions with the emerging modern India).

Goals and Objectives

This thesis aims to investigate how Desai uses memory and time to depict familial relationships and emotional estrangement in post-partition India. This also examines how these narratives reveal the psychological trauma of displacement and familial fractures in the novel *Clear Light of Day*.

Accordingly, this research seeks to achieve the following, articulated through a series of focused objectives that systematically address the overarching aim:

1. To examine narrative techniques that represent the fluidity of time and memory.
2. To explore how personal trauma and historical context intersect in shaping family dynamics.
3. To analyze the symbolic significance of space and silence in Desai's portrayal of emotional distance.
4. To assess how *Clear Light of Day* reflects the tension between tradition and modernity.

Primary and Secondary Materials

Primary Material

The primary material of this research is Anita Desai's *Clear Light of Day*. Primary materials are the original texts or artifacts upon which a study is based; they constitute firsthand testimony or direct evidence concerning the topic under consideration. They present information in its uninterpreted or unevaluated original form.

Secondary Materials

Secondary materials refer to scholarly works that comment on, interpret, or critically discuss the primary source text. These materials may describe primary sources and are often employed to support a specific thesis or argument, or to persuade the reader toward a particular viewpoint. For this thesis, secondary materials encompass various critical books, academic journal articles, and scholarly online resources.

Research Questions

To effectively address the main goals and specific objectives of this thesis, the following research questions will guide the investigation into Anita Desai's *Clear Light of Day*:

1. How does Desai use memory as a narrative and psychological device in shaping character identity?
2. In what ways does post-Partition trauma influence the Das family's interpersonal relations?
3. How does gendered silence function as both repression and resilience in the novel?
4. What does the interplay of past and present reveal about modern Indian consciousness?

Literature Review

The Scholarly opinions and critics' views regarding memory, melancholy, modernity, and familial fractures, or the fragmentation of familial relationships in Desai's *Clear Light of Day*, will be provided in this section. These research works and opinions form the critical framework of this thesis.

According to Yadrami and Gupta, "With the help of memory, Desai uses her literary craft to shape and mould her characters. Memory is used as a tool to travel through the landscape of the past. It helps to achieve a combination of the presence of the past into our changing present and the possibilities of the future" (Yadrami and Gupta, 170). Desai employs memory not only as a thematic concern but also as a psychological and structural framework. She does not follow the linear chronological order to unfold the story; rather, the novel moves fluidly between past and present. This is complemented by Talukder and Biswas in their writing, "The partition movement disintegrates the Das family. The closest relationship between Bim and Raja has broken down with the passage of time" (Talukder and Biswas, 151). About Desai's non-linear treatment of time, Alamgir Hashmi also says: "Indeed, time is an emotional sequence of events rather than a serial imitation of chronological perception. Since the story is told in the stream-of-consciousness style, the linearity of the actual event is not imitated by the writing; the nature of the event is 'emotional' as recollected by the characters..., through whose eyes the reader sees and assesses the situation. With a shifting point of view, and the frequent time lapse, the narrative is realized gradually and gathered skillfully" (Hashmi, 71). The significance of memory in the novel once again aligns with Sudhakar R. Jamakhandi's statement, "the Das home has seen many childhood drama, and it is these that are conjured up in the collective memory of Tara and Bim until, upon their completion. Bim and Tara realize a sense of the worth of their sibling relationship. Tara seeks continuity from her frequent trips

home and achieves a sense of permanence only when Bim too realizes the reason for her return home: the house” (Jamjhandi, 8).

The characters of the novel, the members of the Das family, especially Bim, Raja, Tara, Baba, and Aunt Mira, can be considered as the victims of time. It is nothing but time that creates a boundary between past and present. Time passes, but memory remains alive in the minds of individuals. Time plays the role of both destroyer and preserver as Desai employs in the novel “Time the destroyer is time the preserver” (Desai, 277). Desai remarks about this finest literary work as a “four-dimensional piece”. Daniel Gnanaraj S writes in this regard: “The motif chosen for *Clear Light of Day* is drawn from the poems of Emily Dickinson and T. S. Eliot. They let us know that this will be a novel about memory: about places and people who go through change and transformation to find their true identities” (Gnanaraj, 273).

Anita Desai has used Old Delhi and New Delhi as symbols to demonstrate the distinction between the old and new worlds. “Bim is like a living symbol of Old Delhi - her thoughts, lifestyle, and the whole neighborhood hardly budge when it comes to change” (Biswas and Talukder, 552). Old Delhi represents tradition, whereas New Delhi represents modernity. Old Delhi represents hopelessness, and New Delhi points to hopefulness. “Old Delhi is symbolic of Bim’s life, which is monotonous and has the air of her past. Tara’s life is like New Delhi, which is developing fast” (Sharma, 109).

Several critics situate *Clear Light of Day* within the broader context of post-Partition India, interpreting the novel as a subtle reflection of national trauma. Osman points out that “Desai’s *Clear Light of Day* is categorized within the Partition fiction” (Osman, 15). The effects of partition are clarified by Rituparna Roy’s observation of the Das father’s advice: “This passage in the novel alerts us to the fact of how the specter of the Partition was affecting one and all on the subcontinent in 1947” (Roy, 84). Though the

partition does not directly affect the Das family, indirectly, all the breakdown between the Das siblings occurs due to the Partition. Desai metaphorically presents the fractured relationships between siblings to portray the partition and division of India and Pakistan, or the Hindus and Muslims. This view is supported by Jobaar Talukder's statement, "The growing animosity between Raja and Bim mirrors the broader conflict between Muslims and Hindus, as well as between India and Pakistan" (Biswas et al., 11). The catastrophic events of the Partition caused immense physical and psychological destruction as well as the loss of life among Indians, as "...she is the first introducing deep psychological probing of her characters" (Biswas and Talukder, 2024, p. 549). The familial fractures are also caused by partition; in the novel, Tara leaves the house for a secure life beyond chaos. Raja also leaves initially to help Hyder Ali's Muslim family in the troubled time of partition, and then never comes back home again. A crucial observation made by Jobaar Talukder, "Raja and Bim were once very close, but their relationship deteriorated after Raja decided to move to Hyderabad following a letter from Hyder Ali, who had relocated to Pakistan . . . Raja writes to Bim, stating she can continue living in the family house if she pays the same rent the family had always paid. Bim finds this letter insulting, which fuels her anger" (Biswas et al., 10-11).

The roles of Bim and Tara have been thoroughly studied by feminist critics, who have concentrated on gendered expectations, emotional labor, and silence. Bim is often seen as a symbol of resistance, opposing traditional feminine norms of domesticity and marriage. It has been seen as an expression of autonomy because she chose to stay single and financially independent. Jobaar Talukder argues, "Anita Desai's female characters are not just revolutionary; they possess remarkable strength to confront the repercussions of their choices. . . Bim stands out as an extraordinary woman among the female characters in the novel. She exhibits leadership qualities and an independent spirit, firmly believing in

her individuality and ability to navigate life without being reliant on a man” (Biswas et al., 12). Bim embodies the woman described by Simone de Beauvoir, “who, once she breaks free from dependency, undermines the very foundation of a system built on her reliance. With this newfound independence, she no longer requires a male intermediary between herself and the universe” (Gupta, 158). The gendered silence and patriarchal dominance of this novel are also reflected in Dr. Yogesh M. Sarode’s argument, “Desai reaps the harvest of the circumstances of women’s suffering in her writing to showcase issues that women in society generally experience... She basically focuses on the troubles of contemporary women in a male-dominated society and struggles to vent her” (Sarode, 5186). Other critics like Mohd Asraf Mir and Laila Nargis, in their research paper on feminine sensibility in the novel, have said that “...Bim subverts the traditional model of women. She is portrayed as assertive, firm, and insistent on ruling others rather than being ruled” (Mohd Asraf Mir and Laila Nargis, 2014). These lines clearly state the fact that Bim is not a traditional Indian woman whom this society can suppress. Desai has tried her best to bring out a character through Bim who can cross the limits of the general characteristics of this society.

While these studies critically examine many facets of the novel, not much attention has been placed on how memory and time function in post-partition India to represent emotional distance and familial ties. Thereby, this will serve as the essential basis for this research.

Research Methodology

This study employs a two-pronged methodological approach—”close textual exegeses” and “critical discourse analysis”- to examine how memory, melancholy, and modernity contribute to familial fractures in Anita Desai’s *Clear Light of Day*. Since the research focuses on thematic, psychological, and narrative dimensions rather than empirical data, the methodology relies primarily on close reading and textual analysis, supported by relevant theoretical and critical frameworks.

The research explores how Desai represents individual consciousness, emotional dislocation, and changing family dynamics within a modern Indian context. The research employs close textual analysis as its central method, where the researcher needs to consider three components of the text: Qualitative measures, Quantitative measures, and the Reader and the Task. Each of these is equally important for considering the complexity of a text.

“Close reading” focuses on two tasks:

- a way of reading a text in such a way that you go beyond merely mastering or summarizing the content of a text so that you understand, through reading and annotating, what the text is doing. Close reading tends to be prompted by asking “how”, “why”, “on what terms” as questions, rather than questions of fact (who, what, where, when).
- a way of writing about a text in which the observations and insights produced by reading the text closely serve as your primary form of evidence, supporting your main thesis and its parts.

The first step of close reading is observation, applied to a text or a passage of the text. The aim is to notice all striking features of the text, where content and concept come together. Close readings of the text’s imagery, metaphors, and figurations of mobility,

particularly the partition, gender roles, and familial fractures, will also constitute a key part of this methodology.

The second may include interpretation as rhetorical features (extending to concepts and the vocabulary or methodological points of view embedded in them), structural elements (organization of the writer's main points and presentation of the material on the page), and cultural references (audience/readership). Next, the aim is to notice only selected features of the text—for instance, oppositions and correspondences (ideas in parallel, or concepts that depend on each other to develop over the course of the source) or historical references. Either way, making these observations constitutes the first step in the process of “close textual exegesis”.

To complement this analysis, the research will include a comparative study of the novel's public and critical receptions. Drawing on reviews from general readership sites (such as Goodreads and Amazon) and academic reviews published in scholarly journals. This comparison will examine how *Clear Light of Day* is received by a range of audiences. Particular attention will be paid to points of controversy, such as representations of Islam, gender roles, and cultural stereotyping. This aims to explore how memory functions both as a source of connection and alienation, how melancholy shapes character identity, and how modernity disrupts traditional familial bonds. The analysis remains text-centered while being informed by relevant theoretical perspectives at the same time engages differently with lay readers and academics, offering further insight into the politics of representation and reception.

By combining these approaches, the methodology creates space for a comprehensive examination of how *Clear Light of Day* navigates memory as a narrative, gendered silence in society, partition trauma in shaping the relationships, familial fractures due to emotional distance, and the tension between tradition and modernity.

Theoretical Framework

This study employs selected literary and critical theories to interpret the major themes, character dynamics, and ideological underpinnings of the selected text, *Clear Light of Day* by Anita Desai. This research will utilize an interdisciplinary theoretical framework, which draws upon psychological theory (Object Relations) to examine memory and guilt in sibling bonds, post-colonial feminism (Spivak, Mohanty), which explores female silence, and trauma theory to interpret partition's lingering emotional wounds. The framework ensures that the analysis remains theoretically grounded.

As a central theory for the framework, psychoanalytic theory, specifically "Object Relations Theory" (developed by Melanie Klein), provides valuable insights into exploring the psychological dimensions of memory and guilt, and demonstrates how memory is used to shape the different characters as well as the familial relationships of the Das siblings. Object relations theory emphasizes the significance of early relationships in shaping an individual's personality and emotional responses. In the novel *Clear Light of Day*, Bim's childhood experiences of neglect, responsibility, and loss continue to shape her adulthood. Not only Melanie Klein, but theorists like D. W. Winnicott and W. R. D. Fairbairn focus highly on early emotional bonds and their impact on adult identity.

Trauma theory by Cathy Caruth considers that trauma constitutes a disruption that surpasses conventional human comprehension, which offers a framework in this research to explore how unsolved trauma disrupts memory, time, identity, and relationships. Also, examine how personal trauma shapes family dynamics in the novel. Desai represents trauma as a notion of time that collapses past and present, at the same time destroying familial relationships. In *Clear Light of Day*, trauma operates on both personal and historical levels. Personal trauma, such as the emotional distance of the Das siblings in their childhood, and Aunt Mira's decline. Historical trauma as the partition of India and Pakistan

in 1947 and its aftermath. All of these traumas create psychological wounds and influence the Das family's interpersonal relations. In this context, the character's emotional immersion in the past and the delay in reconciliation are both explained by the trauma theory.

Postcolonial Feminism theory provides a critical framework for analyzing the depth of gendered silence, emotional labor, resilience, and female agency. Feminist theories by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak and Chandra Talpade Mohanty challenge the traditional gender role, domination under patriarchal society, and marginalized voices of women. This theory helps to explore how gendered silence functions as both repression and resilience in Desai's novel, where Bim is represented as a model of silent sacrifice, resistance to defeat, and ultimately a strong voice against patriarchal society. Gayatri Chakravorty's concept of the subaltern shows how women's voices are often marginalized in a patriarchal society. Mohanty critiques the homogenization of "Third World women" and raises the form of women's resistance against domination and discrimination. These concepts are the core of post-colonial feminist theory, which ultimately explores the resistance, responsibility, and identity of women.

Taken collectively, these theoretical perspectives allow for a layered reading of the novel *Clear Light of Day* as a narrative concerning how memory evolves from a source of division into a medium of understanding and reconciliation, how personal and historical trauma destroys family bonds, and finally, how gender functions as a repression and resilience.

Chapter 2

Analysis

The Function of Memory as Psychological Device in Shaping Character Identity

Anita Desai's novel *Clear Light of Day* presents the complicated and fractured relationships between the Das siblings. Desai's non-linear narrative employs memory as both a thematic concern and a psychological device in shaping character identity throughout the novel. Desai's narrative technique also represents the fluidity of time as she uses a loop of the present and the past without a straight chronology. In this regard, A key insight offered by Md. Jobar Talukder & Prakash Chandra Biswas, "Desai has used time and memory to shape her characters and narrative style and to demonstrate how memories influence one's present as well as future" (Talukder & Biswas, 149).

Here, memory is not only a recollection of events throughout the lives of the Das siblings, but rather it is also the governing force of the character consciousness. Past experiences shape the emotional responses of the characters, making them realise their fault. Tara apologizes to Bim for marrying Bakul and leaving, instead of helping her take care of Raja, Baba, and Aunt Mira. Tara, "Bim, I always wanted to say—I can't go away without saying—I'm sorry—I can never forgive myself—or forget—... When I married—and left—and didn't even come back and help you nurse Mira-masi, Bim—whenever I think of that—how could I?" (Desai, 264). Here, Desai clearly represents the effects of memory in shaping the character's identity and shows how memory narrows down the emotional distance.

Memory functions as an inner action through which each character understands the self and builds their identity. In *Clear Light of Day*, characters like Bim's identity is constructed around remembered responsibility and hurt. And these memories shape her self-image as the sacrificial and the one who stayed. She is not even married, and eventually

sacrifices her dreams to take care of the family and her siblings. Dr. Biswas once said to Bim regarding her sacrifice, “Now I understand why you do not wish to marry. You have dedicated your life to others—... You have sacrificed your own life for them” (Desai, 148). These memories ultimately shape Bim’s identity. She never escaped from her responsibilities, whereas Raja and Tara easily escaped. These memories hurt Bim throughout the novel. She accepts the past and is finally ready to forgive Raja when she comes to realize that she loves her family more than anything, “and in their shade she saw how she loved him, loved Raja and Tara and all of them who had lived in this house with her. There could be no love more deep and full and wide than this one, she knew” (Desai, 251).

Memory continues to ache, guilt remains alive, but to engage with them consciously becomes the novel’s ethical summons. Not only is the character Bim shaped by the memory, but also Tara escapes from her bitter memory of childhood. The Das parents hardly care about the Das siblings; Aunt Mira becomes the motherly character for them. This lack of parental affection and bitterness affected Tara in her childhood, and she has not forgotten that memory. She comes from the United States with her husband and feels relieved when she can contrast her life with her childhood. The house may remain the same, but she now feels a more welcoming environment as Desai describes, “But the ice-cream did have, she had to admit, a beneficial effect all round: in a little while, as the students began to leave the house,... the gramophone in Baba’s room stirred and rumbled into life again. Tara was grateful for it. She wished Bakul could see them now—her family” (Desai, 30).

Desai uses the memory of the last in the novel as a reconciliation between siblings. Through Tara’s visit to Delhi and the reminder of all the memories they have shared, Bim realizes that family is the solution to deeper conflicts, and it’s better to leave the bitterness

behind and move forward. Bim tells Tara to visit her as she forgives him and wants to rebuild the relationship between siblings, “Shall I tell Raja—?” ‘Yes,’ Bim urged, her voice flying, buoyant. ‘Tell him how we’re not used to it—Baba and I. Tell him we never travel anymore. Tell him we couldn’t come—but he should come. Bring him back with you, Tara—or tell him to come in the winter” (Desai, 267).

Ultimately, Desai shows the fluidity of time as time passes, but the memories remain in the mind, which shapes the identity and drives towards reconciliation. Taken together, these views suggest that “in foregrounding emotional labour, advocating responsibility through apology, and valuing memory as generative work, Desai contributes a distinctive vision of reconciliation” (Kumari & Pal, 04).

Partition as Historical Trauma: Fractured Interpersonal Bonds within the Das Family

One of the most traumatic moments in South Asian history, the 1947 partition of India and Pakistan had a long-lasting effect on the social, cultural, and family landscapes of the region. Anita Desai’s novel *Clear Light of Day* represents the effects of partition within the Indian culture. She portrays how the partition and its aftermath trauma influence the Das family, the interpersonal relationships between the Das siblings, and the migration of Hyder Ali’s family to Hyderabad. This notion is supported by the statement, “The sibling relationships, especially the strained bond between Raja and his sisters Bimla and Tara, symbolize the fragmented identities and cultural dissonance that arose in the wake of partition” (Biswas et al.).

The central part of the novel is set against the backdrop of Indian independence, particularly the partition of 1947. During the period of the partition of India and Pakistan, a lot of changes were experienced by the masses of India, such as socio-political change, cultural shifting, family fragmentation, etc. The division of Hindu and Muslim families

leads to tension between the similar cultures they share. The masses faced horrific violence and a massive change during the partition and post-partition time. Around 300000 Muslim migrants left Delhi, and roughly 500000 non-Muslim came from Pakistan. “All steps are being taken to carry out the partition smoothly, we hope safely. Refugee camps are being formed” (Desai, 107-108).

Desai shows the partition as a negative force that eventually destroys families, cultures, and relationships. Muslims are likely to become the enemy of the region overnight, and the land will no longer be safe for Muslims. “Safe? For Muslims? Here in India? It will be safe after every Muslim has had his throat slit,” Raja said with great viciousness (Desai, 69). Raja, despite belonging to a Hindu family, had a tendency to read Urdu poetry, and he wanted to be admitted to the Islamic College, but his father rejected and said, “But this is no college for you. It is a Jamia Millia form”(Desai, 77). Before the Partition, it was not unusual or dangerous for a Hindu to study the language of Muslims. Students had the option to choose between Hindi and Urdu, as Desai notes, “before the Partition... students had a choice between Hindi and Urdu” (Desai, 72).

And Raja’s father also cautiously said that, “there is going to be trouble, Raja—there are going to be riots and slaughter,’ ... ‘If you, a Hindu boy, are caught in Jamia Millia, the centre of Islamic studies—as you call it—you will be torn to bits, you will be burnt alive” (Desai, 79). This attitude shows the condition of Muslims at the time of partition. But Raja’s relationships with his Muslim landlord, Hyder Ali, demonstrate the universal human connection and shared cultural values beyond religious barriers. He even leaves his house to help them, “I will not go to bed,’ he hissed, spit flying. ‘I will go—go to—to Hyderabad. Hyder Ali Sahib has asked me to come... I will—go today—today I will catch the train—I won’t stop here, with you, another day” (Desai, 145). This idea is further clarified by the statement of Gairola, “*Clear Light of Day* exposes the deep-seated religious

biases between Muslims and Hindus that persisted in Indian society for decades leading up to the Partition” (Gairola, 2017, p. 124).

The post-partition trauma influences the Das siblings’ interpersonal relations. The breakdown has started from the time of partition. Though the Das family was not directly affected by the effects of partition, the fractures in siblings’ relationships formed based on partition when Raja left the house to help Hyder Ali’s family, and he created a bitter relationship with Bim. He shouted, “I have to go...you don’t think I can go on living just to keep my brother and sister company, do you?” (Desai, 153). Raja leaves, and Bim is left alone to take care of Baba. Raja’s leave for Hyderabad was ultimately the result of partition and its trauma, which created a breakdown in Bim Raja’s relationship as he didn’t return to the house again, marry Hyder Ali’s daughter Benazir, and become the inherits Ali’s property. Raja eventually became the landlord of Bim, and in a letter Raja wrote, “You will have got our wire with the news of Hyder Ali Sahib’s death..., I shall never think of raising it or of selling the house as long as you and Baba need it. If you have any worries, Bim, you have only to tell— Raja” (Desai, 41). This letter made Bim angry and irritated, and their relationship became more bitter as Desai described, “I’m bored with Raja. Utterly bored, . . .’He is too rich to be interesting any more, too fat and too successful. Rich, fat, and successful people are boring” (Desai, 218).

Another familial breakdown highlighted by Desai is the escape of Tara by marrying Bakul for a safe and sound life beyond the chaos. Tara always looked for a modern life, and she decided to marry Bakul to escape. When she left, Bim again feels alone, and the bonding between siblings is destroyed. However, Tara’s actions often align with traditional expectations. Gupta concurs, “attributing Tara’s marriage decision to her longing for attention in the household” (Gupta, 2007).

Therefore, the analysis reveals that post-partition trauma actually affects the interpersonal relationships between the Das siblings. The Das family is not affected directly by the partition's violence, but indirectly, the effects of partition and personal trauma intersect in shaping family dynamics. Raja and Tara's departure was led by the cause of partition in 1947. This is also examined by Dr. Prakash Chandra Biswas, who argues that, "Through the lens of the Das family, the novel poignantly reflects the broader repercussions of Partition on Indian families, elucidating the indirect yet profound negative impact on their survival and cohesion" (Biswas et al.). Not only that, but Hyder Ali's escape from Delhi to Hyderabad was also due to partition, which fragmented the cultural alliances of the region and created an undeclared restriction between the two religious groups.

Gendered Silence as a Mode of Repression and Resistance

Gendered silence functions in two ways in Anita Desai's *Clear Light of Day*: first, it is a method of patriarchal repression; second, it is a resilient tactic used by women to endure, survive, and subtly rebel. Desai demonstrates that women's silences are profoundly significant ethical and psychological spaces. Desai portrays silence in the novel to reflect how women are conditioned to suppress desire, anger, and self-expression within the domestic sphere. In contemporary times of the novel, just after the British colonial rule, women are expected to be self-sacrificing, emotionally restrained, and must be devoted to family rather than self. In the novel, Bim sacrifices her opportunity for self-development for the sake of her family, whereas she always wanted to do something else, even though she denied marrying just because she wanted space and independence, as she notes: "I never went to school, never married, never left the house what use is a life like that?" (Desai 31), but ironically, she plays the traditional woman's role when Tara and Raja leave the house, as well as Baba. This aligns with the statement by Pradip Kumar Bera that, "Bim has devoted her life to helping others, including her mentally challenged brother, her alcoholic

aunt Mira, Raja during his final illness in 1947, and even Begum, the dog of Hyder Ali Sahib” (Bera, 252).

Bim silently accepts what Raja and Tara imposed on her. She automatically became the responsible one in the family. She never leaves her family, whereas Raja did without concern about the future of the family. Raja promises to return to the family “‘Bim, I’ll come back,... ‘Why should you come back?’ Bim asked stonily. ‘Bim, don’t be so hard. You know I must come back—to look after you and Baba. I can’t leave you alone” (Desai, 153-154), but he didn’t come back rather he write a letter about his ownership of the house Bim living and mention the rent of the house at the same time. Here, Desai explores the patriarchal repression as well as Bim’s endurance and survival. Unspoken bitterness toward Raja for leaving the family and toward Tara for getting away through marriage characterizes Bim’s existence. She shows how even an educated, self-reliant woman is imprisoned in emotional silence by keeping her rage mostly to herself. Bim’s silent acceptance and regrates expresses through her monologue, “Why had she chosen Baba to vent her hurt and pain and frustration on? Why had she not written a letter to Raja, pouring out all she had to say to him over the years? Or attacked Tara... the habit of affection and her own insecurity?” (Desai, 250). Her psychological needs are suppressed by this silence, which turns her power into resentment. Here, moral obligation and gendered responsibility turn quiet into a psychological prison. Bim’s devotion to detail, quiet, and aesthetic fixes comes to represent emotional labor. Do her sacrifices lead to freedom or imprisonment? Is it possible for actions of recollection to evolve into feminist self-recognition? Kumari and Pal argue in this regard, “Her self-effacement is steeped in guilt. Psychoanalytic theory suggests this is moral masochism. Bim internalises the perceived failure of the Das family, despite her emotional endurance” (Kumari and Pal, 116).

In the novel, gendered silence and memory are tightly related; women recall things in quiet. Instead of chronicling their emotional pasts, they carry them. This illustrates how women perpetuate family continuity through silent recall in contrast to masculine memory (Raja's letters, goals). Bim does not explicitly protest or dramatize her sacrifice, which makes her apathy to leave the family home and Baba noteworthy. She starts to act morally steadfastly by remaining silent.

Temporal Fluidity and the Emergence of Modern Indian Subjectivity

The home setting, strained family ties, and divergent life decisions of the Das siblings in Anita Desai's *Clear Light of Day* effectively capture the conflict between tradition and modernity. Desai illustrates how tradition and modernity collide in post-Partition India to create moral conflict, emotional estrangement, and brittle identities rather than portraying them as straightforward opposites. Here, 'The Family House' is portrayed as a site of tradition. This old house in Old Delhi, where the Das family lives, symbolizes the traditional Indian value. The story of the novel revolves around the house, and from the past to the present, the house stands as a memory for the Das siblings. The story begins when Tara returns to the old house in the present, and she notices that nothing has changed: "Old Delhi does not change" (Desai, 07). This realization leads to a nostalgic and emotional response, ultimately facilitating the reconciliation of their relationships.

Bim's decision to stay in the old house and take care of Baba represents a commitment to traditional responsibility, as she said, "I can't leave the house—" (Desai, 122). In contrast, Tara and Raja's escape represents the human desire for change and shows the reality of the modern era. They broke the relationships between siblings and withdrew themselves from all the responsibilities, which reflects the cruelty of modernity, when Raja promised to return, "Bim, don't be so hard. You know I must come back—to look after you and Baba. I can't leave you alone" (Desai, 154), but he didn't come back. Not only that,

but Tara also escaped the house for the findings of a safe and modern life, as she admitted, “always leaving us out, leaving us behind—and then Mira-masi becoming so—so strange, and Raja so ill—till it seemed that the house was ill, illness passing from one generation to the other so that anyone who lived in it was bound to become ill and the only thing to do was to get away from it, escape...” (Desai, 238), and this represents Tara’s longing for modern life and repulsion for traditional old house at the young age. Here, a tension was created between two sisters, but at the end of the novel, Tara started to love the old house, and she found herself when she returned to the old house after a long time, and this became the foundation of the re-bonding of siblings. This notion is supported by Hossain, “As Bim’s determination to keep the household running and to define herself counterpoints her sister Tara’s retreat into traditional domesticity, and encapsulate the broader conflicts of modernity and tradition within newly-independent India. Hence the novels focus on revival, both in terms of history and humanity, becomes an exploration of recovery and reconciliation after the fracturing of family and the colonial wound” (Hossain et al.).

Raja embodies modernity and upward mobility. His admiration for Hyder Ali’s Muslim family reflects a break from traditional Hindu domesticity. His response to the letter from Hyder Ali, “I will go—go to—to Hyderabad. Hyder Ali Sahib has asked me to come” (Desai, 145), when it was a crucial time for Muslims, highlights his thoughts of humanity and modernity beyond the traditional division between Hindus and Muslims. But in this response, he leaves his family behind. Modernity here promises freedom but results in detachment from familial obligation, exposing its emotional cost. Hossain’s statement once again argues Raja’s distance from his family: “Raja later took up residence in Hyderabad, his idolatry of Hyder Ali’s family expressing just that emotional distance which separates Raja from his own family” (Hossain et al.).

A catastrophic result of this contradiction is Baba, who is both protected and constrained by conventional care while being ignored by contemporary advancement. As highlighted by Hossain, “Baba, stands as a living example of another kind of damage that has come from such forced migration. Though his illness pre-dates Partition, his constant repudiation (not mutual attraction; total exclusion), his unwillingness to communicate, etc.” (Hossain et al.). He exists beyond the productivity of tradition and the advancement of modernity, revealing the boundaries of both systems when inclusivity and compassion fall short.

Thus, tradition and modernity are portrayed in *Clear Light of Day* as opposing but interdependent forces rather than as moral absolutes. While modernism gives freedom but fosters alienation, tradition offers continuity but necessitates sacrifice. Desai makes the case that realizing the costs and values of each is necessary for both national and personal reconciliation via remembrance, quiet, and home space. As A. K. Srivastava points out in “Indian Writing in English: Tradition and Modernity, 1990, “Desai shows that Indian stories have universal appeal which can transcend cultural boundaries and yet remain faithful to their own cultural roots” (Srivastava, 1990).

Chapter 3

Conclusion

Desai's *Clear Light of Day* unfolds the devastating effects of the India-Pakistan Partition in 1947. Desai has successfully made a comprehensive demarcation between the pre-partition and post-partition life of the Indian people. This thesis has explored *Clear Light of Day* as a novel deeply concerned with the intimate intersections of memory, melancholy, and modernity, and also focuses on how these forces shape relationships of the Das siblings, as well as how these become the reason behind familial fractures. A thorough examination of family dynamics, individual identity, and the larger socio-political backdrop of postcolonial India may be found in Anita Desai's novel *Clear Light of Day*.

Among multiple aspects, memory and time emerge as the central structuring forces of the novel. Memory functions as an active psychological device, and the novel revolves around the recollection of memories. Similarly, the wounds created by time can be healed by time only. The fractured relationships between the Das siblings rebound by the passage of time and by the recollection of memories when Tara returns to their Old Delhi house. Other siblings, particularly Bim, were persuaded to forgive Raja by Tara's recalled memories. Thus, the roles of time and memory cannot be denied or ignored. Here, time is the biggest game changer, and memory provides individuals with unavoidable pleasant or unpleasant feelings. Additionally, melancholy is also closely linked with memory, for Bim in particular, melancholy develops into a chronic emotional state that reflects unresolved sadness, unrecognized sacrifice, and repressed anger. Ultimately, Desai has clearly portrayed how memory can be both unifying and dividing, and how time can be both a destroyer and a preserver.

This thesis examines the Partition's lingering emotional wounds, likewise the indirect yet enduring impact of the 1947 Partition through the lens of Caruth's trauma

theory and postcolonial criticism. Even though the Das family is not directly affected by the violence of partition, the trauma and indirect effects actually lead them towards familial destruction. Raja leaves the house to help Hyder Ali's Muslim family as they face trouble during the partition, and Tara leaves by marrying Bakul for a safe and secure life. All of this trouble in the Das family was caused by the effect of partition and cultural change. Through the lens of the Das family, the novel poignantly reflects the broader repercussions of Partition on Indian families, elucidating the indirect yet profound negative impact on their survival and cohesion.

Gendered silence, analyzed through postcolonial feminist theory by Spivak and Mohanty, has been shown to function simultaneously as patriarchal repression and resilience of women. Through mental toil, sacrifice, and silence, the female character Bim in the novel has maintained family continuity, demonstrating how tradition endures despite unequal gender duty.

Subsequently, the novel's investigation of fragmented subjectivity is highlighted by the conflict between tradition and modernity. Tradition promotes continuity but demands sacrifice, while modernism promises freedom and mobility but creates estrangement.

This thesis has examined *Clear Light of Day* from a completely new perspective. This research is distinctive in part because it employs multiple kinds of theoretical frameworks to examine the identities of the different characters and determine the causes of familial fractures, emotional distance, and other issues.

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